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Lectotypification of the name *Salix pseudodepressa* (Salicaceae)

Nataliya K. Kovtonyuk^{1*} & Irina V. Belyaeva^{2,3}

Nataliya K. Kovtonyuk^{1*}
e-mail: nkovtonyuk@csbg.nsc.ru

Irina V. Belyaeva^{2,3}
e-mail: i.belyaeva@kew.org

¹ Central Siberian Botanical Garden
SB RAS Novosibirsk, Russia

² Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew,
Richmond, Surrey, United Kingdom

³ Institute Botanic Garden UrB RAS
Yekaterinburg, Russia

* corresponding author

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ABSTRACT

Problems with typification of the name, *Salix pseudodepressa* A.K.Skvortsov, are discussed and the lectotypification of this name is made.

Keywords: lectotypification, nomenclature, digital herbarium, Caucasus, flora, *Salix pseudodepressa*, Salicaceae

РЕЗЮМЕ

Ковтонюк Н.К., Беляева И.В. Лектотипификация названия *Salix pseudodepressa* (Salicaceae). Проблемы типификации названия *Salix pseudodepressa* А.К.Сквортсова обсуждены и проведена лектотипификация этого названия.

Ключевые слова: лектотипификация, номенклатура, цифровой гербарий, Кавказ, флора России, *Salix pseudodepressa*, Salicaceae

During work on the digitization of the herbarium collections of vascular plants at the Central Siberian Botanical Garden SB RAS (Kovtonyuk et al. 2019) and on the World Checklist of Salicaceae *sensu stricto* (Belyaeva & Govaerts 2020) the authors of the current paper came across the name, *Salix pseudodepressa* A.K.Skvortsov, that was published in 1966 (Skvortsov 1966a). The author describing this new species made the type citation: “Typus: Armenia turcica (olim Rossiae prov. Kars), prope opp. Sarykamysch, 29 IV 1914 D.I. Litvinov, in herb. Inst. bot. Leningrad; isotypi in “Herb. Fl. USSR” edentur.” In the same year the name was published again (Skvortsov 1966b) and the type was cited on the labels of exiccatae that were distributed to various botanical institutions under the number 4536. However, in the latter case the type citation was corrected to: “Typus: planta nostra; in Herb. Inst. Bot. Acad. Sci. URSS (Leningrad) conservatur. Turcia, prov. Kars, prope opp. Sarykamysch, in palude ad rivulum. Leg. D. Litvinov. 1914 VI 29.” In his later publications, Skvortsov (1968, 1999) used the latter type citation for this species: “Turcia, prov. Kars, prope Sarykamysch, in palude ad rivulum. 29 VI 1914 D.I. Litvinov” (Herb. Fl. URSS N 4536, LE, MW et alibi). Skvortsov’s intention to correct the date of collection is supported indirectly by the existing herbarium specimens in LE that show different stages of development of *S. pseudodepressa* from May to July: LE01044750 (20 V 1902 fragments without developed leaves or catkins); LE01044751 (21 V 1902 fragments without developed leaves but with male catkins); LE01044753 (16 VI 1914 fragments with developed leaves); LE01044752 (7 VII 1910 fragments with developed leaves and catkins with ripened seeds). Comparison of these specimens with the fragments on the exiccatae N 4536

(LE01044748 and LE01044749) makes it clear that the correct month in the type citation in the original publication (Skvortsov 1966a) should be June, not April.

Several exiccatae with the same number 4536 were found: two at LE (LE01044748! and LE01044749!), which were cited by Skvortsov as in the Institute where the type is stored, AAU (D. Litvinov 4536!), C (C10018520!), E (E00235855!) ERE (ERE- general collection 0004891!), L (L1551716!), MHA (MHA0032992!), MW (MW0591818!), NS (NS0002746!), S (S13-14138!), W (W1967-0019592!), US (01269138!). Herbarium codes are given according Triers (2020). As all these exiccatae have the same number, 4536, they belong to the same gathering as is defined in the footnote to Article 8.2 of the ICN and thus are syntypes according to Article 9.6 (Turland et al. 2018), and the lectotype should be chosen. The authors of this paper have already dealt previously with similar cases of typification (Kovtonyuk & Belyaeva 2015, Stepanova et al. 2019) when no exiccatae was marked as the holotype by the author of the published name. Based on Skvortsov’s choice of Institution – LE (first step of typification), one of the specimens, LE01044748, is selected here as the lectotype (second step of typification). The rest of the cited exiccatae under number 4536 from different botanical institutions, which were found using gbif.org portal (GBIF 2020), are isolectotypes.

Salix pseudodepressa A.K.Skvortsov, 1966a, Trudy Bot. Inst. Akad. Nauk Armyansk. S.S.R. **15**: 127; 1966b, Spisok rast. Gerb. fl. SSSR **91**: N 4536. – *S. livida* Goerz, 1930, in Grossheim, Fl. Kavk. **2**: 8; id. 1934, Feddes Repert. **36**: 232. non *S. livida* Wahlenb. – *S. xerophila* auct. non Floderus, 1930: Grossheim, 1945, Fl. Kavk. 2 ed. **3**: 21. – *S. aurita* auct. non *S. aurita* L.: Grossheim, 1945, op. cit. **3**: 20.

Figure 1 Lectotype of *Salix pseudodepressa* A.K.Skvortsov (LE01044748)

Lectotype (designated here): ASIA, Turkey, Kars: Armenia turcica, Sarykamysch [40°20'24"N 42°34'12"E], 29 VI 1914 D.I. Litvinov, N 4536 "Herb. Fl. URSS" LE (LE01044748!). Figure 1.

Isolectotypes: AAU (D. Litvinov 4536!), C (C10018520!), E (E00235855!), ERE (ERE-general collection 0004891!), L (L1551716!), MHA (MHA0032992!) MW (MW0591818!), NS (NS0002746!), S (S13-14138!), W (W 1967-0019592!), US (01269138!).

Distribution. According to Skvortsov (1999), the distribution of *S. pseudodepressa* is limited to the Caucasus. This is a rather rare plant. Its area consists of three isolated locations: in Turkish Armenia (5 known places), Dagestan (13 places), and Balkaria (2 places). It grows in pine and birch stands, on rocks, and in damp depressions in the upper forest and subalpine zones at 1,600–2,300 m.

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